

suiting to rainfed wetland, RAU4009-3 and RAU4009-17, had 6.1 and 6.4% tiller infestation. Of the wetland cultivars, BRI0 was highly resistant (0.2%) (Fig.2). Maximum damage occurred on RAU4009-29 (35.8%), which also had poor tillering (6 tillers/hill). The susceptible variety Jaya had 21.8% silver shoots; the present resistant variety, IET2895, had 6.1%. ■

Honeydew excretion, feeding activity, and insect weight gain as criteria in determining levels of varietal resistance to the green leafhopper

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Studies on the mechanism of rice resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) have used the quantity of honeydew excretion and insect weight gain to determine levels of varietal resistance. These criteria have provided a better assessment of resistance levels than has the seedling bulk screening method. This study was conducted to determine if those parameters could be used to measure the level of resistance to the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. The susceptible variety TN1 was compared with the resistant IR29.

One-day-old adults were starved for 4 hours, weighed individually, and placed in parafilm sachets on 30-day-old plants

Each parafilm sachet contained a day-old adult green leafhopper and served as a replication.

(see photo). There were nine replications for each variety; each sachet served as a replication. After 24 hours, the insects were removed and weighed. Honeydew weight was determined by weighing the parafilm sachet with honeydew, then reweighing the sachet after wiping it dry to remove the honeydew.

The weight of the honeydew excreted on TN1 was only 2.5 times that excreted by hoppers feeding on IR29 (see table). But the weight of assimilated food, which is due primarily to weight gain,

provided more accurate information on the levels of resistance of the two varieties. The weight of assimilated food on TN1 was 13 times that on IR29.

As indicated by the amount of honeydew excreted, feeding was also substantial on the resistant IR29, but most of the intake apparently was not assimilated. Measurements of the amount of food ingested and assimilated can be used to detect levels of resistance to GLH. ■

Comparison of ingestion and metabolic utilization of food of the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* feeding on a susceptible and a resistant variety.^a IRRI, 1979.

Variety	Honey dew wt (mg)	Qty of food ingested ^b (mg)	Wt of as-similated food ^c (mg)	Nutritive value ^d
TN1 (Susceptible)	25.587	26.380 a	0.793 a	0.030
IR29 (Resistant)	10.904	10.966 b	0.062 b	0.006

^aMean for 9 insects starved for 4 hours, then fed on 30-day-old plants for 24 hours. In a column, means followed by a different letter are significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^bQty of food ingested = wt assimilated food + wt of honeydew. ^cWt of assimilated food = insect wt gain or loss due to feeding + wt loss due to metabolism. ^dNutritive value = ratio of wt of assimilated food to wt of ingested food.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Morphological studies of rice varieties that are tolerant of and susceptible to submergence as seedlings

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Varietal differences in submergence tolerance at the seedling stage have been reported. The morphological differences

between submergence tolerant and susceptible rice varieties at seedling stage was the objective of this study.

The seedling height measured in 10-day-old seedlings before complete submergence did not show any significant correlation with submergence tolerance. However, the tolerant varieties were generally taller than the susceptible varieties after complete submergence and recovery.

Although there was no significant correlation between the primary leaf length and survival percentage of plants when submerged in water, the tolerant varieties (all traditional) generally had longer primary leaves than the susceptible varieties (which, except for Leb Mue Nahng 111, were all improved varieties).

Table 1 shows the first and second leaf blades were longer in tolerant